

Determining the Link between Maternal Haemoglobin Levels and the Birth Weight of Newborns: A Retrospective Study

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: To investigate the link between maternal haemoglobin levels and the birth weight of newborns.

Material and Methods: A retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics, MGM Medical College, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India for one year. A total sample of 95 pregnant women was included from data obtained from medical records of pregnant women. The inclusion criteria were pregnant women aged 20–35 years old whereas the exclusion criteria was pregnant women with high parity (more than 4 previous live births), history of abortion, multiple gestation, premature birth, a baby with congenital abnormalities, history of chronic diseases (hypertension, diabetes, asthma, heart disease, tuberculosis, and renal failure) and bleeding during pregnancy (placental abruption and placenta previa).

Results: Of 95 pregnant women included, 44.2% had ever given birth for once (1 parity). The majority were graduated from senior high school (45.3%), and housewife (61.1%). The proportion of maternal anemia and low birth weight were 30.5% and 15.8%, respectively. The mean of maternal hemoglobin level was 11.6 ± 1.2 gr/dl and birth weight was 2927 ± 398 gram. The linear test was used after normality test. It showed p -value=0.783 ($p > 0.05$), this result indicates that there was a linear relationship between maternal hemoglobin level and infant birth weight, as shown in Figure 1. Furthermore, the Pearson correlation test was used to see how close the relationship between the two variables. Pearson correlation test showed that the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was -0.093, indicating a very weak correlation with a negative correlation and value of $p=0.369$ ($p > 0.05$), showing no significant relationship between maternal hemoglobin level and infant birth weight.

Conclusion: To conclude, our study shows that there is no correlation between hemoglobin levels of pregnant women with birth weight. Other factors for low maternal hemoglobin need to be further explored.

Keywords: Maternal Haemoglobin, Birth Weight, Newborns.

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Introduction

Maternal haemoglobin levels during pregnancy have long been recognized as a crucial determinant of both maternal and neonatal health outcomes. Haemoglobin, a protein in red blood cells responsible for carrying oxygen, plays a vital role in ensuring adequate oxygen delivery to the developing foetus. Variations in maternal haemoglobin levels, whether indicative of anaemia or polycythaemia, have been linked to adverse pregnancy outcomes, including low birth weight (LBW) and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Understanding the relationship between maternal haemoglobin levels and the birth weight of newborns is essential for developing effective interventions to improve maternal and neonatal health outcomes. Several recent studies have explored the complex relationship between maternal haemoglobin levels and birth weight. Low maternal haemoglobin levels, often a result of iron deficiency anaemia, are associated with an increased risk of LBW and

preterm birth. [1-4] Conversely, high maternal haemoglobin levels can also pose risks. Elevated haemoglobin levels may indicate reduced plasma volume expansion, leading to decreased placental perfusion and subsequently restricted fetal growth. The mechanisms through which maternal haemoglobin levels influence birth weight are multifaceted. Anaemia during pregnancy leads to reduced oxygen-carrying capacity, compromising oxygen delivery to the fetus and impairing fetal growth. Iron deficiency, a common cause of anaemia, can also affect maternal and foetal immune function, increasing susceptibility to infections that further complicate pregnancy. [5] On the other hand, elevated haemoglobin levels may reflect inadequate plasma volume expansion, which is necessary for meeting the increased circulatory demands of pregnancy. Insufficient plasma volume expansion can lead to reduced uteroplacental blood flow, limiting nutrient and oxygen supply to the foetus. [6]

From a clinical perspective, regular monitoring of maternal haemoglobin levels is essential for early identification and management of both anaemia and polycythaemia. Prenatal care programs should incorporate routine haemoglobin assessments and provide appropriate nutritional interventions, including iron supplementation and dietary counselling, to optimize maternal haemoglobin levels. Additionally, addressing underlying causes of high haemoglobin levels, such as dehydration or chronic hypoxia, is crucial to prevent adverse pregnancy outcomes. Public health initiatives aimed at reducing the prevalence of maternal anaemia, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, can have a significant impact on improving birth outcomes. Programs that enhance access to prenatal care, fortify staple foods with iron, and educate women on the importance of adequate nutrition during pregnancy are critical in addressing this global health issue. [7-12]

Material and Methods

A retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics, MGM Medical College, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India. A total sample of 95 pregnant women was included from data obtained from medical records of pregnant women. The inclusion criteria was pregnant women aged 20–35 years old whereas the exclusion criteria was pregnant women with high parity (more than 4 previous live births), history of abortion, multiple gestation, premature birth, a baby with congenital abnormalities, history of chronic diseases (hypertension, diabetes, asthma, heart disease, tuberculosis, and renal failure) and bleeding during

pregnancy (placental abruption and placenta previa). Data of third-trimester maternal hemoglobin level and birth weight were obtained from the medical record of pregnant women who gave birth after getting ethical approval from the Ethics Committee. Data were collected and analyzed by univariate to find the proportion of each variable, and by bivariate to find the correlation between two variable using Pearson correlation test, with a significant value of $p < 0.05$ using statistical software (SPSS 25.0).

Results

Of 95 pregnant women included, 44.2% had ever given birth for once (1 parity). The majority were graduated from senior high school (45.3%), and housewife (61.1%) as shown in Table 1.

The proportion of maternal anemia and low birth weight were 30.5% and 15.8%, respectively (Table 2). The mean of maternal hemoglobin level was 11.6 ± 1.2 gr/dl and birth weight was 2927 ± 398 gram. The linear test was used after normality test. It showed $p\text{-value} = 0.783$ ($p > 0.05$), this result indicates that there was a linear relationship between maternal hemoglobin level and infant birth weight, as shown in Figure 1. Furthermore, the Pearson correlation test was used to see how close the relationship between the two variables. Pearson correlation test showed that the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was -0.093 , indicating a very weak correlation with a negative correlation and value of $p = 0.369$ ($p > 0.05$), showing no significant relationship between maternal hemoglobin level and infant birth weight.

Table 1 The Baseline Characteristics of Pregnant Women

Characteristics	n=95	%
Parity		
0	39	41.1
1	42	44.2
2	10	10.5
3	4	4.2
Educational Level		
Elementary School	5	5.3
Junior High School	21	22.1
Senior High School	43	45.3
High Education	26	27.3
Occupation		
Working	37	38.9
Housewife	58	61.1

Table 2 Hemoglobin Maternal Level and Infant Birth Weight

Characteristics	n=95	%
Hb level		
<11 gr/dL	29	30.5
11–13 gr/dL	58	61.1
>13 gr/dL	8	8.4
Infant Birth Weight		
<2500 gram	15	15.8
≥2500 gram	80	84.2

Figure 1: The Linear Relationship between Maternal Hemoglobin Level and Infant Birth Weight

Discussion

This study has shown that 30.5% of pregnant women are anemic, and this is slightly lower than the national percentage of 37.1%. The characteristics of the respondents are different compared to the national characteristic in general. Furthermore, these pregnant women have had a normal delivery. In this study, the results show no significant correlation between hemoglobin level of pregnant women with birth weight ($p=0.369$), likewise, in a previous study in other parts of Indonesia in West Sumatra, also has shown no significant correlation between maternal hemoglobin level in the third trimester and infant birth weight.⁷ Many confounding factors cannot be controlled, such as maternal age, parity, nutritional status, chronic disease during pregnancy, genetic factors, characteristics of antenatal care, maternal smoking habits, and socioeconomic condition. [7] These factors may have been taken into consideration. In another study conducted in Africa has shown a similar result that there is no significant relationship between maternal hemoglobin levels and birth weight. [8]

There evidence that various factors may influence condition of anemia and birth weight such as low maternal nutrition before and during pregnancy, age less than 20 years old during pregnancy, abortion history, a history of having a baby with low birth weight, parity

≥ 4 times, women with chronic illness during pregnancy, premature birth, the mother who had multiple gestation, pregnant women that do not consume or low consume of iron tablets, lack of antenatal visits, low maternal education level, and low socioeconomic condition.⁹⁻¹² In our study, most of these factors have been controlled by exclusion criteria, however, several factors are not examined because of the incomplete data in the medical records. Furthermore, several factors that affect birth weight were not studied, such as maternal nutrition

before and during pregnancy, intake of iron tablets, antenatal visits during pregnancy, and socioeconomic condition, whereas it may become a confounding factor in this study. [7,9-13]

Of note, maternal nutritional intake before and during pregnancy can affect fetal development. Poor nutrition in the mother before and during pregnancy can lead to a lack of nutrients that are transmitted through the placenta to the baby.³ Inadequate intake of iron tablets during pregnancy and the lack of antenatal care visits may increase the risk of low birth weight of the baby. [9] The intake of iron tablets during pregnancy helps increasing overall maternal nutrition so it may increase the birth weight of the baby. [9] In antenatal visits, the risk of low birth weight can be reduced because antenatal visits can improve the mother's diet during pregnancy, monitor and assist the mother in weight gain during pregnancy. Socioeconomic conditions have an important role for pregnant women because it affects maternal nutrition before and during pregnancy. [7,12]

Regardless our finding with no association between low hemoglobin during pregnancy and low birth weight, some previous studies have shown otherwise resulting that low hemoglobin level during pregnancy is associated with low birth weight. [14,15] Interestingly, when the severity of anemia in the third trimester of pregnancy is decreased, the average birth weight is increased.⁶

Limitations of this study were that not all influencing factors can be controlled, such as maternal nutrition before and during pregnancy, intake of iron tablets, antenatal visits during pregnancy, and socioeconomic condition. Further study needs to include all of these factors, by doing primary data collection with a prospectively cohort

study method and assessing hemoglobin level from first until the third trimester of pregnancy. As for secondary data, in order to control the factors that

may affect the results, a good medical record is encouraged, such as data of third trimester hemoglobin level, maternal history of the ANC, and keeping medical records in good place, to be used for any later study, and to provide complete information.

Conclusion

To conclude, our study shows that there is no correlation between hemoglobin levels of pregnant women with birth weight. Other factors for low maternal hemoglobin need to be further explored.

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